

LEGAL AND INSTITUTIONAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE DIGITALIZATION OF THE TOURISM INDUSTRY IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract

This article presents a comparative analysis of the role and significance of the digital economy in the tourism and hospitality sectors, using Uzbekistan as a case study. Particular attention is paid to the impact of digital technologies on the development of the tourism industry, including the introduction of electronic visas, e-commerce, online booking, and digital platforms for managing tourist flows. The article analyzes key legal and regulatory acts aimed at the digitalization of the tourism industry, as well as statistical indicators demonstrating the growth of tourist traffic and infrastructure development. The study emphasizes the importance of digitalization as a key factor in enhancing the investment attractiveness and international competitiveness of tourism and the hospitality business.

Keywords: digital economy, tourism, hospitality industry, electronic visa, Uzbekistan, digitalization, tourism infrastructure, international cooperation, public policy, online services.

In recent years, significant work has been done to expand the tourism sector and improve the hotel system. A number of regulatory legal acts aimed at developing this industry have been adopted. In particular, on January 5, 2019, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5611 "On additional measures to accelerate the development of tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan" was published. This decree provided for the first time for a system for issuing electronic entry visas. In addition, this decree approved the Concept for the Development of the Tourism Industry in Uzbekistan for 2019-2025 [1].

Also, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5781 dated August 13, 2019 "On measures for the further development of the tourism industry in the Republic of Uzbekistan" contributed to the widespread introduction of electronic visas, e-commerce and online trading in the tourism and hotel industry [2].

According to official data, Uzbekistan has enormous tourism and recreational potential. There are 7.4 thousand cultural heritage sites in the country, of which 209 are

located in four museum cities - "Ichan-Kala in the city of Khiva", "Historical Center of the city of Bukhara", "Historical Center of the city of Shakhrisabz" and "City of Samarkand". These sites are included in the UNESCO World Heritage List.

In the period from 2010 to 2017, the volume of tourism exports doubled and amounted to 546.9 million US dollars in 2017, and 1,041 million US dollars in 2018. The average annual growth rate of foreign visitors up to 2016 was 8%, in 2017 - 7%, exceeding the mark of 2.69 million people. According to the results of 2018, 5.3 million foreign tourists visited Uzbekistan.

Thanks to measures aimed at supporting and protecting the private sector, the number of tourism organizations, which was 398 in 2015, increased to 950 by the end of 2018, and the number of hotel businesses increased from 661 to 900. Among the key factors that allowed the number of incoming foreign tourists to double in 2018, one can highlight the simplification of the visa regime, rules of stay in Uzbekistan, as well as the conditions for doing business. The following measures were implemented to develop tourism infrastructure and promote tourism potential:

- A visa-free regime has been introduced for an additional 9 countries (18 countries in total);
- The number of countries for whose citizens the procedure for issuing entry visas has been simplified has been increased from 12 to 50;
- A system for processing and issuing electronic entry visas has been launched;
- A procedure for visa-free entry, temporary stay and exit through border points has been introduced for citizens of 101 countries transiting through the territory of Uzbekistan;
- The procedure for temporary registration of foreign citizens on the territory of the republic has been simplified, having been completely transferred to electronic form through the E-MENMON system;
- The procedure for certification of guest houses has been canceled;
- A new mechanism for certification of tourist vehicles designed to carry 8 or more passengers has been introduced, as a result of which in 2018 the fleet of tourist vehicles was replenished with 128 units (47 buses and 81 minibuses) [2].

Of course, the introduction of digital technologies in the tourism and hotel business is not accidental. Currently, the world is seeing a trend towards the growth of the digital economy. International statistical studies also confirm this fact.

In particular, during the analysis of the level of digitalization of the private sector of the European Union economy, conducted by McKinsey, it was found that the level of digitalization is high in finance, telecommunications and media, average in the mining

industry, and low in industries such as agriculture, construction and tourism. The results of the analysis are presented in the following table [3]:

Индекс цифровизации промышленности MGI содержит 20 показателей для измерения цифровых активов, использования цифровых технологий и «цифровых работников» в каждой отрасли экономики

Индекс цифровизации европейской промышленности MGI

Доля реализованного потенциала цифровизации

Analyses also show that even regions and countries that are leaders in the digital economy are unable to fully realize their potential for the implementation of digital technologies. In the United States, the level of digital technology implementation is 18%, while in Europe this figure is only 12% [4].

However, at the global level, there is a positive trend of widespread implementation of digital technologies in various industries. This process is especially pronounced in the tourism sector. The widespread use of smartphones, their gradual reduction in price and increased ease of use accelerate these processes.

The online tourism market is one of the fastest growing sectors of the global economy. And our country is not left out of these changes, as evidenced by the statistics on the growth in the number of foreign tourists visiting Uzbekistan.

Unfortunately, the coronavirus pandemic has dealt a serious blow to the rapidly developing international tourism sector. According to analysts at the Economist Intelligence Unit (EIU), the tourism industry could suffer potential losses of \$80 billion as a result of the pandemic. As new strains and outbreaks of coronavirus continue to emerge, tourist flow remains low [5].

In Uzbekistan, the industry survives thanks to domestic tourism. The situation caused by the pandemic will lead to increased competition between countries to attract foreign tourists. It is the digitalization of national tourism that can help increase the competitiveness of the tourism industry.

N.N. Shakhovalov in his textbook "Internet Technologies in Tourism" notes that today 64% of tourism transactions are made via the Internet, while in other industries this figure ranges from 30% to 40% [6]. The struggle to attract tourists through the digitalization of the tourism industry has already begun. This can be seen in the example of several Asian countries.

In 2018, Sri Lanka launched a large-scale digital promotional campaign aimed at increasing the attractiveness of the tourist destination, which helped attract an additional 2.5 million tourists. Indonesia, which is Sri Lanka's competitor in the tourism sector, launched an internal service Indonesia Travel Exchange (ITX) for booking penthouses and villas. More than 2,000 owners of various properties and hotels joined the network. In Cambodia, the Cambo Ticket platform was created, which allows you to book via email not only ferries, buses and private taxis in Cambodia itself, but also in neighboring countries - Laos, Thailand and Vietnam. I

In Taiwan, a startup called Local Alike was launched, promoting a new concept of local tourism. Within the framework of this online platform, the company plans to unite representatives of the local population around the world who provide tourism services and inform them. In France, the Tripnparty platform operates, helping to find authentic bars and pubs in different countries of the world. The distinctive feature is that these establishments are known mainly to local residents.

The benefits of digital tourism are also reflected in the growth in the number of tourists. In 2019, compared to 2018, there was an increase in visits to countries with a high level of digitalization of tourism. Among them: China (+14%), Germany (+11%), the Republic of Korea (+42%), the USA (+16%), Israel (+24%), France (+12%), Canada (+14%), Switzerland (+12%), Sweden (+50%), Belgium (+25%) [7]. In 2019, 74% of tourists planned their trips through online systems. In Europe, only a third of travelers contacted travel company offices in the traditional way, the rest preferred to use online services and mobile applications to organize their trips on their own. All this indicates the deep penetration of e-commerce and digitalization in the tourism sector.

Unfortunately, the global COVID-19 pandemic has dealt a serious blow to the tourism market and its development. According to the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), 2020 was the worst year in the organization's history. The number of tourists

decreased by 1 billion people (74%) compared to 2019. Revenues in the global tourism industry fell by US\$1.3 trillion, and the number of jobs in the tourism sector decreased by 100-120 million. UNWTO predicted a recovery in the situation by 2023 [8]. However, mutations of the coronavirus and the emergence of new outbreaks of infection have called these forecasts into question.

According to the World Tourism Organization, in the first quarter of 2021, tourism figures were 180 million people (83%) lower than in the same period in 2020. The largest losses (94%) occurred in the Asia-Pacific region, with which Uzbekistan is directly connected [9].

In this regard, a number of regulatory legal acts were adopted in our country aimed at reducing the negative impact of the pandemic on the tourism sector. On May 29, 2020, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan issued Decree No. PF-6002 "On urgent measures to support the tourism industry to mitigate the negative impact of the coronavirus pandemic." In accordance with this decree, numerous benefits were provided for business entities operating in the tourism sector. These included: a 50% reduction in profit tax, the right to carry forward losses to subsequent periods, a temporary cancellation of the tourist tax, the provision of subsidies for attracting tourists, compensation for tour operators' expenses on air tickets and train tickets, as well as additional support measures for travel agencies, tour operators and hotel businesses.

In addition, tour operators and hotels were allowed to partially compensate for expenses and pay salaries to employees through interest-free loans from the Tourism Development Support Fund.

Unlike other sectors of the economy, the restoration and revitalization of tourism directly depends on the tourist flow, and the volume of exports of services in this area depends on the number of foreign citizens visiting the country. Soon after the signing of the above-mentioned decree, on June 19, 2020, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures to develop the tourism sector in strict compliance with the enhanced sanitary and epidemiological safety regime" was adopted. In this decree, one of the key initiatives was identified as tourist insurance, providing for payment of up to 3,000 US dollars in case of coronavirus infection.

In addition, the decree established the mandatory implementation of the "Uzbekistan. Safe travel GUARANTEED" system at facilities serving foreign tourists. It was also stipulated that officials of tourist facilities that have not been certified under this system will be held liable in accordance with the procedure established by law.

On December 9, 2020, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat

Mirziyoyev held a videoconference dedicated to the development of tourism in the context of the pandemic. At the meeting, the targets for 2021 were defined: attracting 1.7 million foreign and 7.5 million domestic tourists, increasing the export of tourism services to \$ 370 million. It was also noted that using the opportunities of pilgrimage tourism will attract 700 thousand pilgrims and ensure the export of services in the amount of \$ 130 million.

In this regard, specific tasks were outlined. As a logical continuation of measures aimed at ensuring the sustainable development of the tourism industry in the context of the pandemic, on February 9, 2021, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan issued a decree "On further measures to develop domestic and pilgrimage tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan." In accordance with this decree, the validity of a number of benefits and preferences was extended until December 31, 2021. Thanks to the timely and effective application of these measures, the country's tourism industry was saved from complete paralysis, and special attention was paid to using the potential of domestic tourism.

At the same time, developments or crises in the tourism industry inevitably affect the hotel sector. Currently, hotels are actively introducing digitalization of all processes - from choosing the type of room and booking it to paying using specialized applications. One of these technologies is Hilton Honors, which is currently being tested. This technology allows users to order hotel services, get acquainted with the hotel map and get access to other necessary services.

In general, the digital platform "Tourism 4.0" is being actively implemented in the world, characterized by the following principles:

- maximum automation of all stages;
- significant contribution and importance of scientific research;
- management of all systems and stages of tourism services using the Internet;
- ensuring the functioning of tourism services based on a single online interaction system.

The Tourism 4.0 system is developing most actively in countries with a high level of digitalization. In general, the rapid development of e-commerce in tourism is observed in the United States, Western Europe, India, Brazil and Russia. China, Chile and other countries with high tourism potential also pay special attention to the development of digital tourism. This means that all countries seeking to develop their tourism potential will inevitably integrate into the e-tourism market.

As a conclusion, the following thoughts can be expressed:

1. The increasing penetration of the digital economy into countries of the world and

the global economy has a significant impact on the digitalization of the tourism industry.

2. The widespread use of mobile phones, the global information network "Internet", including websites, social networks, as well as the availability of systems for ordering services and paying for them through mobile applications create great opportunities for the digitalization of tourism.

3. Against the backdrop of the negative impact of the global pandemic on world tourism, each country is striving to attract more tourists. However, due to the ongoing threat of coronavirus, many people are not yet ready to travel. In such a situation, the flow of tourists will increase to those countries that can create the greatest comfort for them. In this context, digital tourism plays an important role in providing convenience to tourists, and its development directly affects the development of tourism in general [15].

- In our country, the following measures have been implemented to develop digital tourism:

- A system for providing land plots for business activities, including tourism, through electronic online auctions has been introduced.

- A Unified Electronic Register of Residential Leases has been created and is functioning.

- The ability to submit an electronic application for a license for tourism activities has been introduced, which is considered on a "single window" basis.

- In the process of licensing tourism activities, it has become a mandatory condition for the licensee to have its own website, with the ability to make electronic payments and conclude e-commerce agreements with customers.

- Platforms for electronic guides, online purchases of handicrafts and souvenirs have been created.

- An electronic visa and an electronic registration system for tourists have been introduced.

- Despite this, the following factors hinder the development of digital tourism at the global and national levels:

- Regulatory barriers (lack of clear legal documents governing the transition to a digital economy, protection of personal data, control over the accuracy of accounts and the information provided).

- General instability (differences in financial and political capabilities of regions for integration into the digital space).

Low investment in high technologies and start-ups, weak development of technology transfer and import of finished digital products.

- Differences in the standard of living of the population (not everyone has the opportunity to purchase modern functional gadgets, pay for Internet content and roaming services).

Insufficient level of digital literacy of the population (some people are not aware of the possibilities of digital technologies or have only superficial knowledge).

Based on the above, it is advisable to implement the following measures:

- Adopt a state program to provide all regions of the country with high-speed Internet.

- Develop mobile applications and propaganda tools to improve the digital literacy of the population in the field of the digital economy.

- Increase the number and quality of mobile applications, programs and advertising materials representing the tourism potential of Uzbekistan at the international level.

- Digitalize services provided by private households in tourist areas [14].

Develop organizational and legal frameworks for state subsidies, lending or investment in the form of public-private partnerships for start-ups aimed at developing the potential of digital tourism, as well as holding various competitions at the national level.

In recent years (2016–2021), the global demand for such startups has grown by 62%, the purchase of railway tickets through mobile applications by 50%, and the use of tourism services by 65% [13]. The conducted analyses once again confirmed the relationship between economics and law, their mutual influence and regulation. Similarly, the economic and legal regulation of digital tourism plays an important role in its development.

References

1. Uzbekiston Republic Presidential 2019 July 5 January “Uzbekiston Respublikasida tourism zhadal rivozhlantirishga oid kʻyshimcha chora-tadbirlar tugrisida”gi PF-5611-son Farmoni <https://lex.uz/docs/4143188>

2. Uzbekiston Respublikasi Presidential 2019 July 13 Augustdagi “Uzbekiston Respublikasida tourism sohasini yanada rivozhlantirish chora-tadbilari tugrisida”gi PF5781-son Farmoni <https://lex.uz/docs/4474527>

3. World Bank. 2018 Report on the development of the digital economy in Russia, September 2018, "Competition in the digital age: strategic challenges for the Russian Federation".

4. Rodigin L. A., Rodigin E. L. Internet technologies in tourism and hospitality. Lectures [Text]: textbook. manual / RMAT. - M.: Sovetsky Sport, 2014.

5. Abidova D., Khoshimov B. Digitalization in tourism: a step into a new era of industry development. “Iqtisodiyot va innovatsion texnologiyalar” ilmiy elektron jurnali. No. 1, January-February, 2021.

6. Shakhvalov N. N. Internet technologies in tourism. Tutorial. - Barnaul: AltGAKI Publishing House, 2007.

7. Bogomozova I.V., Anoprieva E.V., Klimova T.B. Digital economy in the tourism and hospitality industry: trends and prospects // Service in Russia and abroad. 2019. Vol. 13. Issue. 3. P. 34-47. DOI: 10.24411/1995-042X-2019-10303.8. UNWTO. International Tourism Highlights. URL: https://tourlib.net/wto/WTO_highlights_2020.pdf

9. UNWTO: число международных турпоездок в первом квартале сократилось на 83%. URL: <https://tourism.interfax.ru/ru/news/articles/79149/>

10. URL: <https://www.xabar.uz/jamiyat/shavkatmirziyoyev-videselektor-otkazdi-pandemiyasi-sharoitida>

11. Джанджугазова Е.А. Применения интернет-технологий для сферы туризма и гостеприимства в контексте проблемы освоения профессиональных компетенций. Современная экономика: проблемы и решения. №3(75)

12. Рузиназаров Ш.Н., Ачилова Л.И. Электронный сделки и проблемы их применения в условиях цифрового гражданского оборота (Electronic transactions and problems of their application in a digital civil turnover //development of society and science in the digital economy) // Развитие общества и науки в условиях цифровой. – 2020. - С. 4-25)

13. Черевичко, Т. В. Темякова, Т. В. Цифровизация туризма: формы проявления. Изв. Саратов. ун-та. Нов. сер. Сер. Экономика. Управление. Право. 2019. Т. 19, вып. 1. Стр. 63

14. Ruzinazarov Sh., Achilova L., Rakhmonkulova N. Problems of fundamental scientific and methodological support of digital civil turnover/Journal of Hunan University Natural Sciences <https://johuns.net/index.php/abstract/72.html>

15. Рузиназаров, Ш., & Ачилова, Л. (2017). Актуальные вопросы совершенствования законодательства по обязательствам причинения вреда. Review of law sciences, 1(1).

16. [ПУТЬ ЭВОЛЮЦИИ ИНВЕСТИЦИОННЫХ АКТИВОВ В МИРЕ И В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН](#) ЛМ Бурханова - ББК 65.9 М34, 2024.

17. Бурханова, Л. М. Особенности аккаунтов в социальных сетях как объекта интеллектуальной собственности / Л. М. Бурханова // Правовая защита интеллектуальной собственности: проблемы теории и практики [Электронный ресурс] : электрон. сб. материалов междунар. науч.-практ. конф., Новополюцк, 24 мая 2024 г. / Полоц. гос. ун-т им. Евфросинии Полоцкой, Регион. учеб.-науч.-практ. Юрид. центр ; редкол.: В. А. Богоненко (отв. ред.) [и др.]. – Новополюцк : Полоц. гос. ун-т им. Евфросинии Полоцкой, 2024. – С. 33-41.

18. L Burkhanova [FOUNDATIONS FOR ESTABLISHING THE FACT OF THE UNKNOWN ABSENCE OF AN INDIVIDUAL UNDER THE CIVIL LAW OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN](#) Vol. 2 No. 4 (2023): [International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management](#)

19. Бурханова Л. М. Правовое регулирование права собственности в гражданском праве в условиях совершенствования законодательства: особенности правового статуса субъектов и объектов права собственности при ее осуществлении //Вестник КазНПУ имени Абая серия «Юриспруденция». – 2023. – Т. 74. – №. 4. – С. 34-42.